

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF KNOWLEDGE OF UZBEK MUSIC HISTORY IN FUTURE MUSIC EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this article, the issues related to the process of researching the socio-pedagogical necessity of improving the educational process for the development of the axiological attitude of students to the national musical heritage of future music education teachers are scientifically analyzed.

Key words and phrases: music education, axiological approach, educational process, socio-pedagogical need, research, national musical heritage, quality education..

INTRODUCTION

Today, reforming the educational process of preserving the national musical heritage in our society will help to improve the organization of the innovative educational process aimed at developing the axiological attitude of the students to the national musical heritage. A lot of scientific research work is being carried out on the preservation and study of our classical musical heritage, and scientific conferences are being held to support musical works of art. At the same time, organizational-pedagogical work is being carried out to ensure the educational process of preserving the national heritage, introducing new music to it, and studying foreign co-production. Through this, a new spiritual-educational stage is created. After all, "state support for the preservation, popularization and development of the national values and spirituality of the Uzbek people" will ensure the strengthening of work in this regard. Thus, the national teachers of the future music students will help to develop the axiological music of the students, to provide the profession.

From time to time, production on the ecological environment is related to the origin of changes in the socio-economic situation. In connection with changes in society, the search for new values is precisely social instability. V. P. Zinchenko emphasizes that the 20th century is the period of the highest level of depreciation of universal values. It is for this purpose that in the new millennium, scientific research is actively trying to install and systematize what has been established by mankind [2]. This process also affects education. The axiological way of YA in education basically leads to looking at science, scientific monuments and or the scientific process with a sense of value and following it.

Paying special attention to a certain problem in the pedagogical process is axiologically important in bringing valuable relations to the development of a certain or skill. In scientific knowledge, the reflection of the value of the universe, the things in it, the event, the event, etc. in the human mind, the laws of the understanding of the value in accordance with reality, its level and level, its standards and criteria are extremely important. In addition to general cognitive science, it is based on the data of social and natural sciences, especially the physiology of the higher nervous system, the evidence of sensory organs and mental activity, the achievements of such sciences as logic, linguistics. The understanding of values, the

harmony of emotional and mental knowledge in learning, judgment, generalization of life processes, terms and tools, analysis of axiological processes in natural and social reality, practical activity based on them means an organic process related to each other.

In order to develop the knowledge of the history of Uzbek music in the teachers of future music education, it is planned to start the axiological activity of preserving the musical tradition.

Today, every nation faces the need to preserve values, to form a new attitude to them, and to form their viability based on this. In this sense, the musical heritage as a national value of the people is suitable for the axiological approach and the new approach formed on the basis of this approach. The most effective way to do this is to introduce an axiological approach to education, to form a valuable attitude to the national musical heritage through music education. By developing the knowledge of future music education teachers about the preservation of the national musical heritage, it will be possible to form a valuable attitude to the national musical heritage in students. By developing an axiological attitude to the Uzbek national musical heritage in students, it will be possible to form a musical culture in society and develop axiological responsibility.

The concept of "valuable institution" is also found in the literature on pedagogical axiology. Although many authors use the concepts of "valuable direction" and "valuable ustanovka" as synonyms, M. Rokich was one of the first to distinguish the difference between them. According to the American scientist, ustanovka can be considered as a set of beliefs and beliefs formed over a long period of time, reflected in the subject's attitude towards a certain object (concrete or abstract, personal or social) or situation [3]. So, if orientation reflects a person's harmony with society's norms and human needs, then a valuable attitude reflects a person's readiness to realize this system of relations in practical activities.

As the main principles of the axiological approach, the following were defined:

the principle of integration of social and personal factors that require the formation of a value system in a person. This principle requires students to harmonize social and personal values in the preservation of national musical heritage, to ensure integrity between them;

the principle of social activity. This principle is important and necessary for the preservation of the national musical heritage among students, and the connection with the objective changes taking place in society, including the world of art, requires the development of social activity of the requirements of music education. .

Axiological consciousness, which serves to preserve the national musical heritage, in turn, is inextricably linked with axiological feeling, axiological idpok, feeling of attachment, axiological experience, concept, conclusion and thinking that expresses the content of tradition. In someone, the axiological perception and the feeling of attachment can be manifested more strongly than others, and the feelings related to the feeling of attachment can cause a lot of "upheaval" in his heart. In such a person, it is natural that the responsibility related to the promotion of a certain tradition and the activities related to it are clearly visible when it is closed to others.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Dividing the level of scientific research on the improvement of the training system for the development of knowledge of the history of Uzbek music in future music education teachers into three parts - as studied in Uzbekistan, CIS and Western countries possible

Scientific and practical tasks of developing knowledge of the history of Uzbek music in future music education teachers S. Bulatov, B. Azimov, S. Annamuratova, O. Vasilchenko, Sh. Janaydarov, F. Zorayev, D. Researched by such scientists as Kamolova, H. Nurmatov, F. Khalilov, A. Hasanov. Also, the history, theory, characteristics of Uzbek classical musical heritage, folklore songs, R. Abdullayev, S. Begmatov, T. Vizgo, O. Ibrohimov, F. Karomatov, I. Rajabov, T. Gafurbekov, B. Kadirov, It is covered in the works of M. Kadirov, E. Fayzullayev.

Preservation of national musical heritage in the research of E.Abdulin, YE.Bodina, O.Bochkareva, E.Burzina, N.Ivanov, L.Koval, V.Rajnikov, A.Rapatskaya, YE.Fedorovich, S.Shabaev from the scientists of the Commonwealth of Independent States , the issues of formation of musical culture, formation of axiological attitude to the musical heritage of nations and peoples in different forms and content are studied.

Among foreign scientists, the national musical heritage of the peoples of the world and the development of scientific and organizational projects related to its preservation were studied by scientists such as D. Karomatli, T. Levin, Y. Elsner and A. Yunqlar [4].

RESULTS

Education of the young generation has been one of the most urgent issues in any society. Because the prosperity and development of the society as a society depends on the education of this future generation. It is known that education is a continuous process that regularly affects the preparation of a person for socio-economic production relations in society, as well as his spiritual, intellectual, physical and musical development. The main task now is to provide education and training to these young people, to mobilize their strength and loyalty in the way of strengthening love for this Motherland, peace and tranquility of the country, and strengthening the independence of the republic. It is not difficult to notice this in the wide range of works carried out as a result of the fair policy carried out in our country, as well as in many countries of the world.

The social importance of developing knowledge about the history of Uzbek music in future music education teachers can be justified as follows:

First, the development of society requires the formation of a new worldview in social and spiritual spheres. In this process, researching the development of students' knowledge about the preservation of national musical heritage, preparing future music education teachers for this process, scientific-theoretical study and generalization of the topic based on the achievements in society are of great scientific and practical importance. .

Secondly, the formation of feelings of love for the motherland and confidence in the future is defined as an important issue in the outlook of the young generation. Ensuring the integration of education and upbringing is one of the urgent issues. The fact that the new Law "On Education" specifically specifies the tasks of educating young people who are physically and mentally healthy and have a rich worldview, it is important to deeply study the issues of forming a valuable attitude to the national musical heritage among students. 'requires learning.

Thirdly, the creation of a healthy social environment in the society in the conditions of market relations, its reflection in the minds of young people leads to the formation of socio-political, legal and spiritual views in the spirit of nationalism. This process, in turn, envisages bringing up a morally high generation that corresponds to the new stage of development.

Fourthly, in the process of educating students in the spirit of appreciation of national and universal values, it is important to form their valuable attitude to the national musical heritage. Formation of students' valuable attitude to national musical heritage is not a process that happens by itself. Especially in the conditions of globalization, efforts to devalue national values, efforts to form new public values, and the means of ideological influence become powerful, this issue becomes extremely important.

Before analyzing the social significance and educational features of the development of knowledge about the history of Uzbek music in the future teachers of music education, it would be appropriate to research the national musical heritage, its formation and current status.

Uzbek national music heritage with ancient and rich experience is the main tool for education and upbringing of the young generation. In ancient times, young people who wanted to master the art of music became apprentices to a master artist, lived in his house for years, and absorbed not only the master's skill in art, but also all his good qualities. Over time, the master-disciple tradition served as a foundation for the creation of vocational schools. In the context of the effective activity of such schools, it is expressed that music is a means of professional education in the true sense of the development of a person in society and determining his place.

In the pedagogical process, it is one of the very important issues to inculcate in the future music education teachers the knowledge of music theory and various approaches, as well as the educational, recreational and educational properties of music. In particular, the beauty of music is manifested in the harmony of melody, melody and composition, therefore, good music cleanses the soul, lifts the mood, frees a person from sadness and depression, and frees from defects and mistakes. It will be necessary to explain it based on a new pedagogical methodology. For this, it is necessary to increase the professional competence of future teachers in music education and, through this, to look at musical works and activities with aesthetic taste and understanding, to treat and organize education. Because real music education can be performed only when it is performed with high aesthetic taste.

DISCUSSION

Students majoring in music education have a strong understanding of technology. But many students cannot find the necessary information. Because in today's higher pedagogical education, the information-resource stock of music education is not very rich, as well as it is not properly and efficiently organized for students to study independently and continue extracurricular activities. Therefore, in today's music education, students depend on what the pedagogue teaches during a lesson and are stuck in ineffective lessons. At the same time, most of the students do not know how to analyze the information needed to work in electronic libraries, create a bank of materials on the subject (term papers, articles, documents and abstracts), set parameters (text interval, font). It is necessary to create an opportunity for them to receive independent education, increase their musical knowledge and consolidate what they have learned, and expand information resources.

In the opinion of scientist U.Yuldashev, "forming a future music education system specialist should first of all start with the design of the student's personality. For this, first of all, it is necessary to design qualities and characteristics that will allow him to become a subject of the pedagogical process in the future." This is professional knowledge, skills and

qualifications that determine his professional competence; intellectual-learning ability; ability to do mental work; creativity skills and value-motivation area; It is important to develop artistic-aesthetic knowledge and skills, to cultivate aesthetic sophistication and taste, along with an attempt to develop cooperation, team-organizational, joint, harmonious functioning skills. The integrity and development of these components determines the level of professional mobility of the specialist. Who the graduate will be in the future - whether he is an executive or a teacher, what level of training he has and how many age categories he works with - all this is very important during planning. As a result, determining the student's purpose in life and further activity plans is an important factor in his professional preparation.

Also, the lack of musical instrument playing technique of most students and the poor quality of education, as well as the lack of interest in learning music among students, affect the results. "This situation is also related to the fact that the subject of "Instrumental performance" is held in groups and the study hours given in the curriculum are 2 hours per week for the group.

If we take into account that students have to perform other tasks assigned to them in important subjects, in order to improve their performance skills, the student should do a lot of work on his own. By solving these problems, it will be possible to reform and develop music education. At the same time, it is possible to develop the artistic-aesthetic taste and outlook of future teachers of music education. Therefore, the future music teacher can create high thoughts and feelings, sophistication, joys of the heart, hopes and dreams in students, and increase their creativity [5]. From this point of view, art is always inextricably linked with science, although its purpose is somewhat different than that of science. Because a certain work of art covers social problems that are being studied scientifically.

The pedagogical process aimed at developing the knowledge of the history of Uzbek music in future music education teachers should be focused on forming a valuable attitude to musical culture and Uzbek national music.

In music education and training, the principle of systematicity, scientificity and continuity should be established on a scientific basis in each lesson with its structure and content. The scope of knowledge about music is the main factor of music education and upbringing. It reflects the rules, conclusions, and generalized musical experiences of music created by mankind. Mastering them means creating knowledge and skills in the way of musical practice. In this process, the effectiveness and social importance of the axiological approach is high. Because the axiological approach based on valuable attitude is important in the formation of knowledge about preservation of a certain heritage.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion is that it was found necessary to determine the following main and important factors in researching the pedagogical and psychological foundations of the development of knowledge about the history of Uzbek music in future music education teachers:

☐ In order to develop the knowledge of the history of Uzbek music in the future teachers of music education, first of all, the goal is to form an axiological need for the national musical heritage, to enable them to understand the national need, to influence and improve valuable pedagogical activities aimed at this process. will be a suitable job.

☒ Nowadays, it is difficult to imagine a music lesson without special equipment. Properly equipping the classroom for music lessons creates a creative environment and the necessary musical-emotional mood for students. Various musical instruments, technical and demonstration tools are needed in the lesson. Their quality, timely availability and use often ensure the success of a music lesson.

☒ Debate clubs for the development of knowledge about the history of Uzbek music in future music education teachers; "Discussion puppies" (on improving musical thinking); discuss ideas; intellectual games ("Positive boys and girls", "Tournament of music connoisseurs", "We are national music carriers"); role-playing games; series of video lectures on healthy lifestyle; game-training sessions; talk show; It is effective to develop active and interactive forms and tools such as concert-action ("Maqom Festival", "Foreign Etradasi").

☒ The scientific-theoretical, spiritual-enlightenment, cultural heritage of thinkers who made a great contribution to the formation of music science in general theoretical and practical aspects, as well as music, music scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of the science of education should have knowledge of scientific research works and the ability to use them effectively in the educational process.

☒ In the pedagogical process, it will be possible to inculcate the educational, relaxing and educational properties of music by teaching the knowledge of music theory and different approaches in the future music education teachers.

☒ Physiological and psychological characteristics of future music education teachers are different from the traditional forms of explaining topics in lessons, directly telling, explaining, and showing the necessary information. It ensures that lessons are organized in a different way, making effective use of forms that serve to make them more interesting.

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